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D6.8- Financial strategy and guidelines for CCLs

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
AAL	Average annual loss; synonymous to EL
AARL	Average annual residual loss
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
DRF	Disaster risk financing
DRM	Disaster risk management
EL	Expected loss; synonymous to AAL
EP	Exceedance probability
EU	European Union
EUSF	European Union Solidarity Fund
IPCC	The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
WP	Work package
SOP	Standard operating procedure

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city living labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Koper, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1. **Context and purpose.** This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534. This report specifically focuses on presenting financial strategies and guidelines for the project's frontrunner and follower Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) to manage climate-related risks. The strategies are built upon previous project work, including risk assessments (D6.4, D6.5), and aim to empower municipal decision-makers with actionable, evidence-based approaches for financial resilience.
2. **Methodology.** The core methodology adopted is a comprehensive Disaster Risk Financing (DRF) framework, which encompasses several key phases: (1) understanding risk, (2) implementing risk management actions (including risk reduction, retention, and transfer), (3) designing risk finance instruments, and (4,5) developing a risk management strategy through risk layering (see table below). This approach recognizes that robust climate resilience plans require sufficient and reliable financial resources distributed across all phases of a Disaster Risk Management (DRM) strategy. The project utilizes probabilistic risk models that incorporate both historical data and projected climate scenarios, specifically the Representative Concentration Pathways, RCP 4.5 (intermediate emissions) and RCP 8.5 (high emissions), as adopted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

DRF phase	Components	Description
1 Understanding risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exposure ▪ Hazard ▪ Risk ▪ Resilience targeting (risk acceptance) 	Quantify and understand risk, then define resilience target to enable risk-informed action.
2 Risk management actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk reduction ▪ Risk retention ▪ Risk transfer 	Design a DRM plan, consisting of risk reduction, risk retention, and risk transfer components.
3 Risk finance instrument design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk holder ▪ Purpose ▪ Timing ▪ Risk level 	Use situational analysis to define underlying need and inform instrument requirements.
4 Risk finance instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Taxonomy 	Select appropriate DRF instruments.
5 Risk finance strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk layering 	Combine DRF instruments to create an efficient DRM strategy using a risk layering approach.

3. **Resilience targeting is the first step to establishing a risk financing strategy once risk is understood.** Risk acceptance, or resilience targeting, involves defining the level of residual risk that will not be actively managed through ex-ante financing after reduction, retention, and transfer mechanisms are utilized. This reflects the risk holder's tolerance, budget constraints, and regulatory obligations, often set at a specific return period loss (e.g., 1-in-200-year event).

Figure 1.1. Computed fluvial flood loss exceedance curves with EBA are shown for historical and RCP4.5 climate scenarios for the three frontrunner CCLs. 1-in-200 year-loss can be interpreted as the level of loss that is expected, on average, to be exceeded once every 200 years.

4. Then, three risk management actions that form the backbone of any DRF strategy:

- **Risk Reduction:** The primary focus for risk reduction is on Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) measures. EBAs are nature-based solutions designed to reduce the level of hazard exposure. The effectiveness of these measures in diminishing overall risk directly influences the residual risk that needs to be managed financially.
- **Risk Retention:** This involves mechanisms for accessing capital from internal reserves or pre-arranged external sources for which the risk holder is responsible for repayment. Reserve funds are a straightforward form of risk retention, suitable for managing high-frequency, low-severity events. While offering immediate access to funds, they require initial establishment and replenishment, and there's an opportunity cost associated with tying up capital.
- **Risk Transfer:** This addresses low-frequency, high-impact residual risks by transferring them to external entities like insurance companies or capital markets. This converts potentially catastrophic losses into predictable premiums, stabilizing municipal finances. Parametric insurance is a notable risk transfer instrument that triggers payouts based on a measurable index (e.g., flood depth) rather than assessed damage. This offers advantages like lower costs, faster payouts, and reduced moral hazard, though basis risk (discrepancy between index payout and actual loss) is a consideration. The payout function, defined by an attachment point (trigger) and an exhaustion point (maximum payout), is central to parametric product design.

Figure 1.2. Risk layering.

5. **Risk Finance Strategy: Layered DRF is the core principle.** The document advocates for a layered DRF architecture, a tiered set of financing instruments matched to the frequency and severity profile of losses. The concept is illustrated in Figure 1.2. This approach aims for cost efficiency by using cheaper sources for frequent, smaller losses and more expensive instruments only for catastrophic events. Core advantages include cost efficiency, budget stability, and speed of fund delivery. Typically, risk retention (e.g., reserve funds) covers low-risk layers, risk-pooling or contingent credit addresses medium-risk layers, and market risk transfer (e.g., parametric insurance) is used for high-risk layers.
6. **Risk finance instruments: there are no one-size-fits-all instruments; the choice on where and how to use each revolves around knowing and balancing their trade-offs.** We provided guidance across various DRF instruments (table below), from which a subset is used in analysis to provide guidance on risk financing strategies.

DRF layer	Typical loss return period (RP -- yrs)	Preferred instrument	Key decision variables
Retention	RP < 1-in-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reserve fund ➤ Budget contingencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reserve target (% of operating budget) ➤ Budget reallocation rule
Risk-pooling / contingency credit	1-in-5 < RP < 1-in-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ National solidarity fund ➤ EU Solidarity Fund ➤ Contingent credit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Trigger definition ➤ (credit) draw-down ceiling ➤ repayment tenor
Market risk transfer	1-in-15 < RP < 1-in-200	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Parametric/index-based insurance ➤ Catastrophe bond 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Attachment, Exhaustion ➤ Limit ➤ Trigger index ➤ Premium cap
Exceptional measures	RP > 1-in-200	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Post-event borrowing ➤ International aid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Debt-sustainability threshold

7. **Several assumptions have been baked into a Decision Strategy Support (DSS) Tool (software) that was developed to evaluate and configure these risk layers.** The tool searches for optimal solutions that minimize costs for each unit of mitigated loss. This tool considers baseline risk, risk transfer/retention variables, budget constraints, and resilience targets to identify a Pareto frontier of optimal strategies. These solutions represent the *best* trade-off between financing cost and residual loss. One such illustrative case with commentary is shown below.

It should be emphasized that these solutions are heavily influenced by assumptions – key ones listed below – such as *insurance market cycles* and *opportunity costs*, which require periodic re-evaluation.

Maximum capacity of the reserve fund	Annual Budget	Insurance Attachment point	Insurance Exhaustion point	Portion of exposure ceded to insurance
[0, €1 m]	[0, €0.2 m]	[0, Exhaustion Point]	Min(€10 m, 1:200 loss ¹)	[0, 1]

8. **Illustrative assessment for Massa:** EBA implementation is pivotal; it could slash annual average losses from €750,000 to €25,000, potentially bringing comprehensive risk financing within reach.
- Massa faces prevalent fluvial flooding, with historical annual average residual losses² (AARL) around €0.75 million, potentially rising to €1.5-€3.0 million under the RCP4.5 climate scenario.
 - There are significant uncertainties in tail losses due to climate change; the 200-year fluvial flooding loss varies from €1 million (historical) to €4.4 million (RCP4.5).
 - The city's assumed yearly budget for DRF is €0.2 million, with the pre-EBA AAL being roughly three times this budget.
 - Lack of systematic national budget allocation for disaster risk management blurs lines between layers and hinders informed decision-making; funding often comes ex-post via national calls for proposals, which are slower and costlier than other risk pooling options.
 - (Risk Reduction, EBA) EBA implementation is a top priority, estimated to reduce flood risk by up to 97%, slashing AAL from €750,000 to €25,000. A cost-benefit analysis for this EBA is needed.
 - (Risk Retention) After EBA, frequent residual losses are estimated to be very small, requiring only modest reserve top-ups (less than 5% of budget) before ceding the remaining risk up to the resilience target.
 - (Risk Transfer) The 1-in-200-year tail loss (€1-€4 million depending on the scenario) can potentially be financed by parametric insurance within a yearly budget of less than €80,000 (referencing Sol2 for RCP4.5, 2015-2065). The total risk for city-owned assets is considered too small for catastrophe bonds or risk pools currently.
 - (Overall Strategy) The DRF strategy analysis, assuming EBA is implemented, favours ceding a large portion of the tail risk due to the shape of the loss exceedance curve (small frequent losses, larger tail

¹ These values are read from CCLLs respective EP curves provided as part of D6.5.

² Residual loss is the amount beyond the resilience target for which no ex-ante risk financing is pursued. Average annual residual loss (AARL), is the yearly expected loss remaining post-EBA (risk reduction), risk retention, and risk transfer.

losses). The city aims to manage all losses up to its resilience target and has identified that EBA is key to reducing DRF costs. Massa could explore sharing its DRF experience and options for a city-level risk pool in the future.

9. **Illustrative assessment for Oarsoaldea:** Extremely high frequent losses (€16M for a 1-in-10-year event) and modest EBA impact create a lead to a large protection gap. With an assumed yearly budget of €200,000, the city faces an average annual net residual loss of €3.2M – after retention and transfer – that needs to be covered by ex-post state or international aid.

- The region faces significant exposure to fluvial flooding, with a baseline AAL of approximately €3.5 million.
- Oarsoaldea exhibits a very flat EP curve: a frequent (1-in-10 year) loss is estimated at €16 million, while the tail loss (1-in-200 year) is €31 million, suggesting further risk-reduction measures (first layer) are best prioritized.
- Climate projections (RCP4.5, 2045-2095) suggest only modest amplification of tail risks.
- (Risk Reduction, EBA): The EBA in Oarsoaldea yields a modest reduction in baseline risk. The city is incentivized to consider exploring additional risk reduction solutions.
- (Risk Retention) The DSS tool analysis suggests retaining most risk through reserves, maxing out the assumed yearly budget of €200,000. However, the frequent 1-in-10-year loss (€16 million) far exceeds the maximum assumed reserve capacity of €1 million.
- (Risk Transfer) Due to the high cost of insuring frequent losses, optimal solutions favour minimal insurance coverage. Under an RCP4.5 (2015-2065) scenario, a 1-in-200-year loss is €38.5 million.
- (Overall Strategy & Gaps) The average annual residual risk remains extremely high at around €3.5 million, indicating a significant budget shortfall. The city would struggle to reach even a 1-in-5-year resilience target with its current constraints, facing a protection gap of approximately €10 million after considering reserves and an example insurance strategy (Sol11). The primary protection gap lies in the risk-reduction layer. Oarsoaldea is recommended to explore alternative risk reduction measures in addition to a pre-arranged regional risk pool or contingent credit line.

10. **Vilanova:** Despite significant risk reduction from EBA (cutting expected losses from €4M to €1.85M), remaining frequent losses (1-in-10-year residual loss is estimated at €8.7M – based on historical scenario) still overwhelm the retention and transfer capacities secured by an assumed yearly €200,000 budget, indicating a persistent protection gap and an average annual net residual loss of around €1.1M.

- Fluvial flooding is the dominant hazard, with a baseline AARL of approximately €4 million, likely exceeding the municipal budget without national aid.
- The EP curves point to a large difference between frequent and rare losses: 1-in-10-year loss is €5 million and 1-in-200-year loss is €18 million (historical estimates).
- Climate projections (RCP4.5, 2015-2065) indicate a potential 33% increase in computed tail loss.
- (Risk Reduction, EBA): The EBA is estimated to have significantly slashed risk (e.g., AARL from €4.0m to €1.5m; over 50% reduction in tail loss). A cost-benefit analysis is then conducted and should ideally be integrated into the DRF strategy.

- (Risk Retention) With EBA implemented, the DSS tool analysis (Sol1 for RCP4.5) suggests retaining most risk through reserves, with the yearly budget maxed out at the assumed €200,000. However, the frequent 1:10 loss post-EBA is still estimated at €8.7 million, exceeding the maximum reserve fund size of €1 million.
- (Risk Transfer) As frequent losses remain high and costly to insure, optimal solutions suggest minimal insurance coverage.
- (Overall Strategy & Gaps) The average annual net residual risk remains high at around €1.1-1.7 million (between historical and RCP4.5 projections), indicating a budget shortfall and a protection gap even for frequent losses that cannot be absorbed by the reserve fund. There's a large protection gap across all DRF layers. Vilanova is incentivized to first explore further risk reduction measures at both city, and critical infrastructure levels. Then, in addition to seeking ways to increase its budget, it should also explore city- or region-level risk pools or other meso-layer risk retention mechanisms such as contingent credit lines to address its significant residual risk.

11. Key strategic considerations and guidance for follower CCLs emphasize:

- a. **Prioritizing Risk Reduction:** EBA and other measures can significantly lower overall DRF costs and should be the foundational layer. For instance, in Massa, EBA solutions showed potential to reduce flood risks by up to 97%.
- b. **Understanding Loss Exceedance Probability (EP) Curves:** Unique EP curves for each CCL are crucial for determining the optimal mix of risk retention and transfer. It also uniquely facilitates resilience targeting, which without the EP curve becomes an arbitrary target.
- c. **Setting Context-Specific Resilience Targets:** Targets must reflect local priorities, risk appetite, and financial capacities, defined through stakeholder engagement. 1:200 model loss is among the most used target to plan against.
- d. **Need for Contingent Credit:** These offer efficient financing for moderate-frequency events without the opportunity costs of large reserves. Most CCLs likely to have no access or experience with such instruments. However, as we see it, this is a missed opportunity for the CCLs to reduce their disaster losses at lower costs.
- e. **Diversifying Financial Instruments:** A mix of insurance, bonds, contingent credits, and reserves enhances effective risk management across different layers.
- f. **Exploring EU-Level Mechanisms:** EU-level catastrophe bonds or regional risk pools can bridge financing gaps and lower premium costs through economies of scale. There's a growing call for such instruments.
- g. **Dynamically Adapting Strategies:** Annual reassessments are vital due to changing macroeconomic conditions (e.g., insurance market cycles, opportunity costs).
- h. **Enhancing Communication and Coordination:** Strong links with national and EU institutions can shift focus from reactive ex-post funding to proactive ex-ante financial planning.

12. **In conclusion**, this deliverable provides a comprehensive framework for CCLs to develop robust financial resilience strategies. The optimal approach combines thorough risk assessment, strategic risk reduction, prudent risk retention (including contingent credit), and targeted risk transfer using instruments like

parametric insurance. Continuous stakeholder engagement, regular strategy reviews, and strengthened EU-level collaboration are paramount for ensuring the long-term resilience and fiscal sustainability of Europe's coastal communities in the face of climate change.

A set of infographics summarizing the key aspects of the developed financial strategies for the frontrunner CCLs, as well as a set of general guidelines that can underpin the development of such strategies for municipalities exposed to climate-related risks, are provided in Appendix B: Infographics.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

The present deliverable (D6.8) was developed in the context of WP6's Task 6.5.

Financial strategy and guidelines for CCLLs, uses the results obtained in Task 6.4 (Financial resilience strategies) and takes up the relevance of the concepts of the results shown in Task 6.3 (Residual coastal risk assessment), to produce this deliverable that concludes the tasks of WP6. The guidelines presented in this work will serve as a basis to provide decision makers with a better understanding of disaster risk management and how the constant analysis of available financial instruments is crucial to achieve resilience financial strategies. It is therefore essential that the information and concepts of this work are clearly transferred to both frontrunner and follower CCLLs.

The hazard maps used to perform the quantitative risk assessment were provided by WP3. Additionally, the development of the Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBAs) was a collaborative effort involving the frontrunner CCLLs and WP7.

A close and continuous interaction between WP6, WP7 and WP2 and the CCLLs has been ongoing during the project activities. The results of WP6 and WP7 were co-created with the direct contributions of the CCLLs and the integration of feedback from the frontrunner CCLLs. Moreover, within WP2 activities, WP6 was in direct contact with the CCLLs during the Knowledge Transfer Sessions and presented the WP deliverables to the frontrunners. All feedback from the participants was collected and taken into account in the revision of the deliverables of Task 6.5 and in the preparation of this deliverable D6.8. Therefore, the co-creation of deliverable D6.8 is certainly based on the direct interaction between CCLLs, WP2 and WP6 during the project activities.

With regards to the validation of the deliverable D6.8, the CCLL Board meetings will play a key role in this respect. These meetings will be organized until the end of the project (as part of the Task 2.6 and Task 2.8) and will be a direct channel for presenting the guidelines and collecting feedback from key stakeholders and decision makers.

The Policy Recommendations (D7.5) delivered by WP7 will align with the outcomes of Tasks 6.4 and 6.5, addressing financial resilience and residual risk management after the implementation of EBA measures. This approach will support both the financial sustainability and effectiveness of adaptation measures in coastal cities.

TABLE OF CONTENT

1. Introduction	17
1.1. Background _____	17
1.2. Purpose _____	17
1.3. Methodology _____	18
2. Understanding risk.....	20
2.1. Risk acceptance _____	23
3. Risk management actions	26
3.1. Risk reduction _____	26
3.2. Risk retention _____	26
3.3. Risk transfer _____	27
4. Risk finance	30
4.1. Overview _____	30
4.2. DRF Instruments _____	30
4.3. Risk layering _____	32
5. DRF Strategies for CCLs	36
5.1. General _____	36
5.2. Guidance for frontrunner CCLs _____	39
5.3. Guidance for follower CCLs _____	48
6. Appendix A: Decision Support Tool	51

6.1. Dataset preparation	51
6.2. Optimization objectives	51
6.3. Optimization variables	52
6.4. Constraints	53
6.5. Optimization method	53
6.6. Pareto Optimal Solutions	54
7. Appendix B: Infographics	55

INDEX OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1. Computed fluvial flood loss exceedance curves with EBA are shown for historical and RCP4.5 climate scenarios for the three frontrunner CCLLs. 1-in-200 year-loss can be interpreted as the level of loss that is expected, on average, to be exceeded once every 200 years.	6
Figure 1.2. Risk layering.....	7
Figure 2.1. Components of risk.....	20
Figure 2.2 Fluvial flood Loss Exceedance Probability (EP) curves for Massa with and without EBA risk reduction. .	21
Figure 2.3. <i>An EP curve showing the 1% probability of having losses of €10 million or more. The same datapoint illustrated on an alternate view that expresses return periods. The curves provide a snapshot of both frequent, lower-severity losses and rare, high-severity losses, allowing stakeholders to gauge the impact of different types of consequences that may befall the exposure or portfolio being evaluated.</i>	22
Figure 2.4. Illustrative risk layering diagram for Villanova using modelled loss for RCP4.5 climate scenario and corresponding return periods. 1-in-200-year loss corresponds to €23 million. If 10-year is marked as threshold for risk retention, Villanova might need to cede around €15 million of risk to cover the exposure considered in exposure modelling for the city.	25
Figure 3.1. Example of reserve fund to finance frequent losses over time and possible shortfalls.	27
Figure 3.2. Payout function of an index-based insurance product	29
Figure 4.1. Risk layering in DRF. Taken from Denaro et al (2024).....	31
Figure 4.2 Interpretation of the Pareto front for Massa, fluvial flood with (after) EBA, historical climate scenario, 1956-2005.....	35
Figure 5.1. Computed fluvial flood loss exceedance curves with EBA are shown for historical and RCP4.5 climate scenarios for the three frontrunner CCLLs. 1-in-200 year-loss can be interpreted as the level of loss that is expected, on average, to be exceeded once every 200 years.	37
Figure 6.1. Risk curve fitting	53
Figure 6.2 Example of a Pareto front.....	54

INDEX OF TABLES

Table 1.1. Disaster risk finance steps.....	18
Table 4.1. Risk layering and instruments.....	31
Table 4.2. Key constraints and assumptions used in solution optimization by the DSS tool.....	34

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Managing climate-related risks is increasingly critical for cities as they face heightened exposure to severe weather events driven by climate change. Within the project, significant efforts have been devoted to developing a robust framework for quantifying and managing these risks, specifically targeting coastal city living labs (CCLs). Building upon extensive work carried out in earlier stages of the project, particularly deliverables D6.4, "Residual risk assessment report for the frontrunner CCLs," and D6.5, "Risk profiles for the frontrunner CCLs," the current deliverable (D6.8) synthesizes these earlier insights to propose comprehensive financial resilience strategies.

The developed financial strategies account for the intricacies of climate risk management, explicitly distinguishing between high-frequency, low-impact risks manageable at the municipal level and low-frequency, high-impact risks better addressed through external risk transfer mechanisms such as insurance or parametric solutions. Recognizing the complexity inherent in making financial decisions under uncertainty, the project has established strategies tailored explicitly to mitigate the socio-economic consequences of severe weather events, ensuring financial sustainability and community resilience.

1.2. Purpose

The primary purpose of this deliverable, D6.8 "Financial strategy and guidelines for CCLs," is to provide actionable, evidence-based financial strategies and guidelines tailored for both frontrunner and follower coastal city living labs (CCLs). These guidelines aim to empower municipal decision-makers by offering clear pathways for financially managing residual climate risks identified in prior assessments. Specifically, this report serves to:

- Describe the methodologies used in deriving optimized financial resilience strategies.
- Present a detailed analysis of financial instruments suitable for different types of risks, highlighting the optimal balance between risk retention (municipal funds) and risk transfer (insurance mechanisms).
- Outline strategic recommendations informed by comprehensive stakeholder consultations and quantitative risk assessments.
- Provide guidelines that capture lessons learned from frontrunner CCLs, facilitating practical and adaptable strategies for follower CCLs.

Through this deliverable, city leaders and policymakers will gain access to robust, transparent, and replicable frameworks enabling informed decisions on risk finance, fostering enhanced resilience and fiscal prudence in the face of future climate uncertainties.

1.3. Methodology

Climate resilience plans can work when accompanied by finance. Sufficient and reliable financial resources need to be distributed across different phases of an overarching Disaster Risk Management (DRM) strategy that a nation or a municipality enacts and embraces in its operations. In this work, we focus on the aspects of (1) understanding risk, (2) risk management actions, (3) risk finance instruments, and (4) risk management strategy through risk layering. These key Disaster Risk Financing (DRF) concepts are illustrated in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Disaster risk finance steps

DRF phase	Components	Description
1 Understanding risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exposure ▪ Hazard ▪ Risk ▪ Resilience targeting (risk acceptance) 	Quantify and understand risk, then define resilience target to enable risk-informed action.
2 Risk management actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk reduction ▪ Risk retention ▪ Risk transfer 	Design a DRM plan, consisting of risk reduction, risk retention, and risk transfer components.
3 Risk finance instrument design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk holder ▪ Purpose ▪ Timing ▪ Risk level 	Use situational analysis to define underlying need and inform instrument requirements.
4 Risk finance instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Taxonomy 	Select appropriate DRF instruments.
5 Risk finance strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk layering 	Combine DRF instruments to create an efficient DRM strategy using a risk layering approach.

The focus areas of this assessment are the following:

- **Risk understanding and quantification:** We utilize the probabilistic risk models developed in prior deliverables, including baseline risk and climate scenarios formally adopted by The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).
- **Risk reduction:** We incorporate the evaluated ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) measures to compute post-reduction (residual) risk and explore risk financing strategies for the CCLs.
- **Risk retention:** Risk retention instruments are pre-arranged mechanisms that provide risk holders access to capital, where funds are sourced either from their own reserves or external capital that they are responsible for repaying. The resources provided through these instruments come from those affected by the disaster. In other words, those affected by the disaster are those who retain the responsibility for covering the costs that arise following the event. Emphasis is placed on the use of reserve funds.
- **Risk transfer:** Analysing the technical and economic feasibility of risk transfer instruments, including insurance, and more particularly parametric solutions.

- **Risk acceptance (resilience targeting):** Resilience targeting defines the cutoff point between the portion of risk addressed through a DRM strategy and the [residual risk](#) that lies outside the scope of active management. Where this resilience threshold is set reflects the risk holder's tolerance, as well as practical factors such as budget constraints and regulatory obligations. For instance, one might establish a resilience target corresponding to impacts expected at a 200-year return period
- **Risk layering:** A practical approach to adopting the most cost-efficient management strategy, depending on the type of risk, is referred to as risk layering. A strong conclusion in the literature on contemporary disaster risk management is that risk financing instruments should be integrated within an overall DRM strategy. The process should involve *"identifying the various layers of disaster risk, who bears each level of risk, and the possible risk transfer instruments available to each layer"* ([Miller and Keipi 2005](#)). Successful, evidence-based applications, continue to emerge (e.g., [GIZ 2019](#), [Hochrainer-Stigler & Reiter 2021](#), [UN 2023](#)).

Ultimately, this workflow aims to provide structured guidance to establishing evidence-based financial strategies tailored to the specific resilience needs and priorities of both frontrunner and follower CCLs.

2. UNDERSTANDING RISK

Effective financial resilience strategies can only be established on the back of robust risk quantification. The methodologies applied for quantifying risk combine probabilistic modelling techniques encompassing current and projected climate scenarios (Figure 2.1). These analyses yield essential metrics such as hazard curves, [loss exceedance probability curves](#), and [average annual losses \(AAL\)](#), providing insight into the extent and frequency of potential impacts.

Figure 2.1. Components of risk

Detailed knowledge of pre- and post-intervention (through EBA) risks helps municipalities formulate strategic decisions grounded in robust evidence. By accurately quantifying risks, municipalities can prioritize interventions, financial planning, and resource allocation effectively, thereby optimizing their overall resilience. Here, risk assessment is carried out for three climate scenarios to account for a plausible range of uncertainties involved in the weather-related phenomena that are investigated:

- **Historical baseline**, assuming what transpired between 1965–2010 is acceptable to be used for estimating the impacts of future disasters.
- **RCP 4.5**, described by the IPCC as an intermediate scenario. Emissions in RCP 4.5 peak around 2040, then decline.
- **RCP 8.5**. Emissions continue to rise throughout the 21st century. RCP8.5 is generally taken as the basis for worst-case climate change scenarios.

Risk models – like the ones presented in previous deliverables of this for for the CCLLS – allow the quantification of the probability and severity of disaster impacts for a given set of exposure and hazard types. These models are made to guide stakeholders to make informed decisions around the choice of the *limit of indemnity* (for risk transfer) against disasters. One such analysis performed for Massa, one of the frontrunner CCLLS is shown in Figure 2.2.

Typically, insureds (like governments and municipalities) buy to the modelled *1-in-250-year return period loss*, which is a commonly used return period in exposure and risk management. In other words, risk of incurring financial losses up to that return period are transferred to third parties. More conservative returns of 500 or 1,000 years also can be used depending on a mix of decision variables and stakeholder priorities such as risk aversion, strategic importance of the insured asset(s).

Fluvial flood risk curves

Figure 2.2 Fluvial flood Loss Exceedance Probability (EP) curves for Massa with and without EBA risk reduction.

Return period

The concept of return period is key when dealing with natural hazard data. It can serve as both an analytical unit and a descriptive term. For example, financial loss with an annual probability of exceedance of 0.01, representing the loss amount that is expected to be exceeded once roughly $(1/0.01)$ 100 years – hence the 100-year loss, 1:100 loss, or 1-in-100-year loss. Here, the return period functions as a unit of analysis.

Return periods are also commonly used to characterize specific historical or potential hazard events. A term like "100-year flood" or "1-in-100-year flood" refers to a flood intensity with a 1% chance of occurring in any given year. However, this should not be conflated with 1-in-100-year loss caused by floods.

Although often interpreted as an event or loss that happens once every 100 years, this is a statistical average—such floods may occur in back-to-back years, within a few decades, or more than a century apart.

What is an EP Curve?

An EP (Exceedance Probability) curve expresses the probability that losses will exceed increasing thresholds within a defined period, usually a year. The curve answers the fundamental question: “What is the likelihood that a certain loss level will be exceeded?”. Otherwise, “On average, how often a (e.g., financial) loss of €X million might be exceeded in the next 365 days”.

$$\text{Loss Return Period} = 1/(\text{Exceedance Probability})$$

$$\text{Exceedance Probability} = 1/(\text{Loss Return Period})$$

Below, the X-axis represents loss values (often measured in millions of dollars/euros), while the Y-axis shows the probability that the specified loss threshold will be exceeded in the specified time frame.

Figure 2.3. An EP curve showing the 1% probability of having losses of €10 million or more. The same datapoint illustrated on an alternate view that expresses return periods. The curves provide a snapshot of both frequent, lower-severity losses and rare, high-severity losses, allowing stakeholders to gauge the impact of different types of consequences that may befall the exposure or portfolio being evaluated.

Assume the EP curve shows that the 1% EP is USD 100 million. The way to interpret this datapoint would be:

- The exposure has a 1% probability of experiencing losses of € 20 million or greater each year.
- As a long-term average, a loss of €20 million or greater in a year will occur once every hundred years.
- A loss of USD 100 million has a return period of 100 years (since $1/.01 = 100$)

EP curves play a crucial role in strategic decision-making for insurers, enabling them to assess and price risk, plan for catastrophic events, optimize risk financing strategies, inform regulatory compliance, and enhance stakeholder confidence.

What about the Average Annual Loss (AAL)?

Expected Loss (EL), also known as Average Annual Loss (AAL), represents the long-term average of financial losses from evaluated natural disasters in a single year by integrating over all possible events and their probabilities. For policy makers, this single metric provides an indication of the annual budgetary provision needed to cover average disaster costs, guides cost-benefit analyses of mitigation measures by showing how much risk can be offset per euro invested and supports comparing risk exposure across regions or sectors without focusing solely on rare extreme events.

2.1. Risk acceptance

Risk acceptance – interchangeably called as *resilience targeting* – addresses the management of net residual risk that remains after *risk reduction*, *retention*, and *transfer* mechanisms are exhausted. In other words, it corresponds to the level of loss beyond which no ex-ante risk financing is pursued.

Acceptance does not imply neglect but rather acknowledges that some risk levels are either economically infeasible or technically impractical to transfer or further mitigate. Effective risk acceptance criteria are defined based on transparent, objective, and stakeholder-informed parameters. For example, a municipality might set acceptance criteria based on a clearly defined threshold of affordability or budgetary constraints. Risks falling below a certain monetary impact or within manageable frequency levels might be accepted and managed internally through annual budgeting and contingency reserves. This ensures clarity in financial planning, helping municipal decision-makers prioritize resource allocation more effectively.

Therefore, formulating sound *acceptance criteria* necessitates considering:

- modelled risk estimates: some definition of rare loss – such as 1-in-200-year modelled loss (definition in Pg. 21, see also)
- historical loss experience
- socio-economic impacts
- stakeholder priorities: budgetary limitations are among chief determinants here.

Establishment of said criteria is within the purview of the risk manager on behalf of the stakeholders. Well-established risk acceptance criteria ensure that the retained risk remains within tolerable and manageable boundaries, enabling resilient municipal operations and long-term fiscal stability.

Residual risk

Residual risk is the amount of risk that remains after having applied a risk reduction layer — measures that reduce exposure, hazard or vulnerability. Using average annual loss (AAL) as our metric, “residual AAL” is simply the AAL we calculate once the mitigation is in place. Because residual AAL will always be lower than the baseline (pre-mitigation) AAL, a smaller gap between the two indicates a less effective (though not necessarily less cost-effective) solution.

Net residual loss

The term *net* residual is instead used to refer to the level and size of risk that remains beyond the resilience target that is not managed through ex-ante instruments any more.

The resilience target is generally set at the portfolio level to some definition of rare loss such as 1-in-200-year modelled loss in DRM spheres. This threshold can be:

- moved between 100-to-250-year modelled loss combining fluvial and coastal flood risks depending on various criteria relating mostly to risk acceptance criteria.

- set for baseline, or any other climate scenarios for which loss exceedance curves are provided, reflecting stakeholders' level of risk aversion and stance with regard to the increased uncertainties around mean loss estimates caused by climate change (Calel et al, 2020).

The resilience target directly corresponds with the coverage limit (or exhaustion point for index-based coverages) after retained risk is deducted from total. The concept is illustrated in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4. Illustrative risk layering diagram for Villanova using modelled loss for RCP4.5 climate scenario and corresponding return periods. 1-in-200-year loss corresponds to €23 million. If 10-year is marked as threshold for risk retention, Villanova might need to cede around €15 million of risk to cover the exposure considered in exposure modelling for the city.

3. RISK MANAGEMENT ACTIONS

3.1. Risk reduction

Existing catastrophe risk can be reduced by either reducing hazard, exposure, or vulnerability – the three components of risk. This project focuses on Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EBA) measures, which is a form of hazard reduction. EBAs contribute significantly to reducing the level of hazard that the built environment is exposed to in the form of climate impacts through sustainable, nature-based solutions. Detailed information on the EBA drawn up for the front-runner CCLLs have been provided in previous deliverables of this study. Such interventions are assessed for their effectiveness in diminishing overall risk, thus directly influencing the residual risk profiles that cities must manage.

The identification and assessment of residual risks post-EBA implementation determine the extent to which additional financial mechanisms, such as insurance or municipal reserves, will be necessary. Thus, a precise evaluation of EBA's risk mitigation effectiveness. This report and the work presented herein base themselves on the post-intervention (namely, with EBA) conditions as '*Baseline*'. As such, no additional assessment or analysis on the effectiveness of EBA will be presented.

3.2. Risk retention

Risk-retention refers to the quick access of capital by risk holders, where funds are sourced either from their own reserve funds or external capital that they are responsible for repaying, such as pre-arranged credit lines and contingencies. The resources provided through these instruments come from those affected by the disaster. Reserves are suitable to finance low-severity, high- frequency events ([UN 2023](#)).

A reserve fund, a straightforward form of an instrument for risk retention, involves setting aside cash reserves in anticipation of disasters. This approach offers immediate and complete access to funds without incurring premiums or surcharges on the saved amount. However, there are notable considerations. The reserve fund needs to be established initially and replenished after each event and subsequent drawdown, making it vulnerable to potential shortfalls if multiple events occur consecutively or if the reserve is insufficient. In such cases, losses may remain uncovered, necessitating borrowing which may be very expensive or not available entirely. The indefinite maintenance of reserve funds, until an event occurs, poses political challenges as it can be difficult to justify, especially when prevention measures may not yield immediate political dividends. Additionally, there is an opportunity cost associated with tying up a certain amount of money indefinitely. Figure 3.1 illustrates this dynamic: as events of variable severity produce damages, the reserve fund (green line) may or may not be able to cover the losses (uncovered losses, in blue), subsequent events (e.g., event 2 and event 3) may leave even relatively small losses uncovered, conversely, reserves may grow very large and become unsustainable between events (e.g., event

4 to event 5). Consequently, this type of tool proves efficient and sustainable primarily for high-frequency, low-severity risks where a relatively small reserve is sufficient ([Denaro et al 2024³](#)).

Figure 3.1. Example of reserve fund to finance frequent losses over time and possible shortfalls.

3.3. Risk transfer

Risk transfer plays a crucial role in a comprehensive financial resilience strategy, specifically addressing *low-frequency but high-impact* events and [residual risk](#). Its primary objective is to stabilize municipal financial conditions by converting uncertain and potentially catastrophic losses into predictable and manageable financial obligations in the form of premiums. By transferring risks to external entities, such as insurance companies or capital markets, municipalities can protect their budgets and ensure solvency even when facing extreme events.

Risk transfer

Consider a coastal city exposed to infrequent but severe storm surge events. Without risk transfer, a single catastrophic event could exhaust municipal reserves, jeopardizing essential public services. By purchasing insurance coverage – such as an index-based product that is much easier to administer with fast payouts – with policy terms and conditions tailored to its risk profile, the city converts potential large losses into predictable yearly premiums, ensuring financial stability and continuity in critical municipal operations.

³ S. Denaro, C. Valerio, G. Bussi, E. Fagà, E. Karaferi, D. Tsarpalis & D. Vamvatsikos, 2024. Financial risk management for earthquake disaster: a case study of Rhodes and Granada. The World Conference in Earthquake Engineering (WCEE24), Milan, Italy.

The efficacy of risk transfer mechanisms depends significantly on careful evaluation using baseline risk estimates. Indicators such as the Average Annual Residual Losses (AALR), loss exceedance probabilities, and probable maximum losses (PMLs) associated with well-defined and communicated return period – which are computed as part of this project – provide critical data points for decision-making. These analytical measures enable municipalities to objectively assess coverage options, optimize insurance limits and deductibles, and balance premium affordability with effective risk protection. In essence, risk quantification is pivotal to sufficiently equip municipalities to make informed, economically sound risk transfer decisions, thereby enhancing overall financial resilience and reducing uncertainty associated with climate-driven disasters.

Parametric insurance

Parametric insurance, a distinct insurance variant, diverges from indemnity insurance in its payout mechanism (Shah et al. (2018)⁴. While indemnity insurance bases payouts on actual damage assessed by an expert, parametric insurance triggers payouts through a measurable index acting as a proxy for real losses. This approach offers several advantages. Firstly, it incurs lower transaction and administrative costs, resulting in more affordable premiums. Secondly, parametric insurance mitigates concerns related to moral hazard and adverse selection. Thirdly, it ensures swift claims resolution and payouts, a crucial factor in the aftermath of natural disasters such as earthquakes (Goda et al. (2015)⁵. Despite these benefits, a potential downside exists in the form of basis risk—a disparity between the index (and consequent payout) and actual losses. Nevertheless, parametric insurance stands as a compelling option, particularly in scenarios where quick claims resolution and cost-effectiveness are paramount considerations.

There are some considerations for the use of parametric or index-based insurance at subnational level:

- **DRF layering:** Cities typically rely first on contingency reserves, emergency budgets or municipal bonds; parametric cover can serve as the next “layer” of pre-arranged finance, automatically releasing funds when triggers are met; finally, national solidarity funds or post-disaster loans kick in for longer-term recovery⁶.
- **Meso-insurance model:** A municipality (or a non-profit/civic intermediary on its behalf) becomes the policyholder, pays premiums, and then redistributes payouts to affected communities or services—removing the need for individual claims processes. This model was piloted in New York City for low-income households via a parametric flood policy purchased by the *Center for NYC Neighborhoods* to fund emergency grants within days of a flood⁷.
- **Regulatory clarity:** In the EU, EIOPA notes that only around 10% of insurers offer parametric products. And regulatory frameworks (e.g. Solvency II) may need adaptation to recognise index-based covers⁸.

⁴ Shah, H. C., Dong, W., Stojanovski, P., & Chen, A. (2018). Evolution of seismic risk management for insurance over the past 30 years. *Earthquake Engineering and Engineering Vibration*, 17, 11-18.

⁵ Goda, K., Wenzel, F., Daniell, J., Beer, M., Kougioumtzoglou, I. A., & Patelli, E. (2015). Insurance and reinsurance models for earthquake. *Encyclopedia of earthquake engineering*, 1184-1206.

⁶ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10669-023-09929-8?utm>

⁷ Environmental Defense Fund 2024. <https://www.edf.org/sites/default/files/2023-11/Harnessing%20Risk%20Transfer%20Report%20Final.pdf>

⁸ A&L Goodbody 2025. <https://www.algoodbody.com/insights-publications/parametric-insurance-a-possible-solution-to-irelands-nat-cat-risk>

Case-in-point: Swiss Re's FLOW product

Swiss Re's FLOW index-based cover: Launched in 2019 for European corporates and public-sector clients exposed to river-level extremes. FLOW uses defined river gauge triggers across major basins (Rhine, Danube, Po, Seine, Thames, etc.) and can be tailored for municipal clients (ports, water utilities, riverside tourism) to insure emergency costs before state aid arrives.

The payout function (Figure 3.2) is a central consideration in the design of a parametric insurance product. It determines payout as a function of a pre-determined index that is either tied to direct observational data about the phenomena or modelled.

- **Attachment Point (AP):** This represents the threshold above which the policy contract is triggered, and a payout becomes due. It essentially acts as the starting point for financial coverage.
- **Exhaustion Point (EP):** This marks the threshold or policy limit beyond which the maximum payout is triggered. It sets the upper limit for the coverage offered by the policy.
- **Retention of Losses:** Losses falling below the Attachment Point (deductible) and above the Exhaustion Point are retained by the policyholder. This ensures that the policyholder bears some of the financial burden.
- **Constant Payout Beyond EP:** As the modelled loss surpasses the Exhaustion Point, the corresponding payout remains constant and is equal to the Coverage Limit (CL). This means that once the losses exceed the maximum payout threshold, the policy provides a consistent level of financial coverage.

$$\text{payout} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } ML < AP \\ ML & \text{if } AP < ML < EP \\ CL & \text{if } ML > EP \end{cases}$$

Figure 3.2. Payout function of an index-based insurance product

4. RISK FINANCE

4.1. Overview

Building on the quantified [residual risk](#) presented in D6.4 and D6.5, this chapter lays out a Disaster Risk Financing (DRF) architecture that is embraced by risk carriers across the globe – from corporate to insurers and governments at nation and subnational levels. The organising principle is layered DRF: a tiered set of financing instruments that match the frequency-and-severity profile of coastal-climate losses and that are activated sequentially, beginning with the cheapest source of funds and progressing to the most expensive only when truly catastrophic losses occur.

Layered DRF

“A layered approach not only allows the development of strategies and financial tools ex-ante, but also the protection of the government’s budget through a better understanding of future financial needs related to potential disasters. Risk layering ensures that cheaper sources of money are used first and that the most expensive instruments are used only in exceptional circumstances. A layered approach to DRF using different financial instruments to bridge financial gaps identified according to the country’s risk profile.”⁹

Core advantages of risk layering are:

- **Cost efficiency** – Placing routine, low-severity losses in the municipal budget or emergency reserve fund avoids paying an insurance premium for events that can be absorbed locally.
- **Budget stability** – High-severity, low-frequency losses threaten fiscal solvency; shifting them to parametric – or index-based – insurance, reinsurance or capital-market instruments converts a volatile liability into a predictable annual premium.
- **Speed & flexibility** – Pre-arranged finance delivers cash within days, complementing risk reduction measures such as the proposed EBAs whose benefits materialise over decades.

Figure 4.1 visualises the concept and serves as a reference diagram for the subsequent sections of our DRF strategy guidance.

4.2. DRF Instruments

Table 4.1 demonstrates key mechanisms and decision variables that are considered for each DRF layer. Note that return period thresholds can be tightened or relaxed according to each CCLL’s risk appetite and fiscal space. Risk finance instruments and aspects of design remain outside the focus of this work and are not discussed in detail in this work. The reader is referred to [Mechler et al \(2014\)](#) for further reading on DRF instruments.

⁹ UN (2023). Report on DRF for PIC.

Table 4.1. Risk layering and instruments.

DRF layer	Typical loss return period (RP -- yrs)	Preferred instrument	Key decision variables
Retention	RP < 1-in-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reserve fund ➤ Budget contingencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reserve target (% of operating budget) ➤ Budget reallocation rule
Risk-pooling / contingency credit	1-in-5 < RP < 1-in-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ National solidarity fund ➤ EU Solidarity Fund ➤ Contingent credit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Trigger definition ➤ (credit) draw-down ceiling ➤ repayment tenor
Market risk transfer	1-in-15 < RP < 1-in-200	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Parametric/index-based insurance ➤ Catastrophe bond 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Attachment ➤ Exhaustion ➤ Limit ➤ Trigger index ➤ Premium cap
Exceptional measures	RP > 1-in-200	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Post-event borrowing ➤ International aid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Debt-sustainability threshold

Figure 4.1. Risk layering in DRF. Taken from Denaro et al (2024)

4.3. Risk layering

Effective layered DRF strategies are devised by combining risk retention and transfer after reduction in a cost-effective (i.e., risk-based) manner. As a rule of thumb, an economic and pragmatic approach is to aim to reduce risk first (i.e., through EBA), then to arrange risk retention, followed by risk transfer¹⁰. Resilience targeting precedes risk transfer by informing key decisions around scope and size.

Workflow

The Decision strategy support (DSS) tool developed as part of D6.6 and D6.7 is used to evaluate and configure said risk layers in search of optimal solutions that minimize costs for each unit mitigated loss. The tool is composed of three parts:

- **Input block** – baseline risk (i.e., the AARL), risk transfer (index-based insurance only) and retention variables (reserves only), municipal budget constraints, and resilience target (risk acceptance) set to 200-year loss.
- **Optimisation engine** – searches thousands of combinations of deductibles, limits, reserve targets and premium caps.
- **Output block** – Pareto frontier showing the trade-off between financing cost (AASC) and residual loss (AARL); sensitivity dashboard revealing which parameters drive strategy performance.

Optimal solutions are shortlisted only if they sit on, or very close to, the Pareto frontier and satisfies stakeholder affordability constraints.

Several parameters define these strategies. For instance, determining the optimal size of the reserve fund is crucial to ensure it effectively covers high-frequency losses while remaining economically viable in terms of opportunity cost and political feasibility. Additionally, decisions regarding the extent of insurance coverage, which involves determining how much risk should be transferred to an insurance company, are essential. This decision-making process is complex, as it involves not only the monetary costs associated with the strategy but also its socio-economic impact. For example, the unavailability of critical infrastructure following a flood event can significantly affect economic activities and social well-being. Ensuring financial coverage for prompt repairs and assistance extends beyond mere financial considerations and has substantial implications for the overall resilience and functionality of the city. Therefore, considering the socio-economic and political dimensions is crucial for city officials when selecting the most appropriate strategy. For this reason, the strategies were designed to optimize two different objectives:

- Minimizing the total cost of the strategy, Average Annual Strategy Cost (AASC)
- Minimizing the Residual (uncovered) Average Annual Losses (RAAL/AARL).

The result is a set of Pareto optimal alternatives. In this context, a Pareto optimal solution refers to a scenario where no objective can be improved without worsening another. Details of the tool – in addition to the demonstrators D6.6 and D6.7 deliverables – are presented in [Appendix A: Decision Support Tool](#).

It is important to note however, these findings are strongly influenced by a set of parameter assumptions that concern the DRF instruments used in layering, namely:

¹⁰ Disaster Risk Finance – A Toolkit. GIZ 2019.

- ☛ **Insurance pricing** – Prices for insurance and reinsurance policies vary significantly and are influenced by factors including but not limited to the underlying risk, capital that the insurer needs to hold relative to the risk, desired rate of return, how correlated the risk is to the rest of the portfolio ([SOA 2017](#)). The technical pricing formulae depend on both the expected loss and its standard deviation. The loads on EL and standard deviation will vary according to the specific use case. Furthermore, insurance markets alternate between phases of ‘soft’ and ‘hard’ pricing (phases marked by expansion and contraction of insurance availability, and associated deflation or inflation of insurance premium costs) ([Giz ACRI+, 2019](#)).
- ☛ **Opportunity cost** (or *risk-free* rate of return on investment) – Currently assumed at 5%, subject to fluctuations depending on global macro-economic indicators and trends. This number should be adjusted periodically to account for variations. Opportunity cost punishes holding reserves instead of investing them or converting them to other liquid (cash-equivalent) assets like bonds that yield interest.

It is for this reason that no single risk layering strategy can remain the most cost-effective. As such, they need to be dynamically adjusted to the variables of the environment. As the insurance market transitions between soft to hard pricing cycles and the cost of capital (i.e., opportunity cost) fluctuations, risk managers must re-evaluate their strategies and react to changing conditions by rebalancing their risk layering. Optimal risk layering solutions are presented in the following based on the above-said assumptions.

Optimal Pareto Solutions

Figure 6.2 presents a Pareto front generated by the DSS tool, plotting annual average strategy cost (AASC) against the corresponding annual average residual loss (AARL) for a suite of layered risk-financing strategies. Each marker (Sol1–Sol20) represents a unique combination of parameters like reserve-fund size, annual contributions, and insurance terms and conditions for the complete list of parameters). The front visualizes how increasing spending in reserves and insurance reduces expected losses—and where those reductions begin to taper off. By slicing this curve into three regions, decision-makers can clearly see which cost bands deliver the greatest loss mitigation per euro spent and thus build capacity to negotiate and align local risk-financing plans with regional and national partners.

Note that all Pareto Solutions are subject to constraints, and all CCLs share constraints such as maximum yearly reserve fund intake and annual budget for DRF¹¹. Some key variables are listed in Table 4.2. Therefore, solutions shown and discussed in the following remain hypothetical rather than endorsements. It is the administrators of DRF

¹¹ See [Comprehensive Approach for CCLs](#)

The insights gleaned from the frontrunner CCLs collectively underscore the importance of comprehensive, evidence-based strategies. Effective DRF strategies integrate robust risk reduction, layered financial instruments, clearly defined resilience targets, and flexible adjustment mechanisms sensitive to evolving macroeconomic conditions.

In conclusion, the optimal disaster risk financing approach combines robust risk assessment, strategic risk reduction, judicious risk retention—including contingent credit options—and targeted risk transfer through carefully designed parametric products. Continuous stakeholder engagement, regular strategic reassessments, and strengthened EU collaboration emerge as key practices to ensure resilience and fiscal sustainability across Europe's coastal communities.

Appendix A: Decision Support Tool

– within their respective remit and purview – that make the final decisions by blending their priorities in with evidence-based decision variables such as those provided by this analysis.

Table 4.2. Key constraints and assumptions used in solution optimization by the DSS tool

Maximum capacity of the reserve fund	Annual Budget	Insurance Attachment point	Insurance Exhaustion point	Portion of exposure ceded to insurance
[0, €1 m]	[0, €0.2 m]	[0, ExhaustionPoint]	Min(€10 m, 1-in-200-year loss ¹²)	[0, 1]

¹² These values are read from CCLs respective [EP curves](#) provided as part of D6.5.

Risk layering using the DSS Tool

Segment 1: Low-Cost, High-Yield (~ €0 – €3,000). In the left-hand “elbow” of the front we see the steepest trade-off: every additional €1,000 of strategy cost shaves off roughly 1,700€ of annual residual loss (AARL).

- Sol20 at ~€300 → AARL ≈ 80,000 €
- Sol10 at ~€1,000 → AARL ≈ 78,000 €
- Sol4 at ~€3,000 → AARL ≈ 75,000 €

Interpretation: In this range, modest investments in reserve-fund top-ups or low-coverage (yellow markers indicate higher reserve fund spending as % of total) insurance cut expected losses. While it appears like a sweet spot for the CCLs to rapidly build protection capacity at minimal outlay, the figures are negligible.

Segment 2: Mid-Cost, Moderate Returns (~ €3,000 – €50,000). Here the curve flattens: each extra €1,000 now only reduces AARL by 500€

- Sol8 at ~€11,000 → AARL ≈ €71,000
- Sol9 at ~€21,000 → AARL ≈ €65,000

Interpretation:

At this stage, we’re adding capacity—higher attachment points or larger reserve drawdowns—but we see diminishing marginal benefits measured by reductions in AARL. That said, we understand by examining the solution table that a much larger portion of the return period losses are ceded through insurance.

Segment 3: High-Cost, Diminishing Returns (~€50,000+). Beyond €50,000, the curve nearly plateaus: an extra €1,000 buys only 50€ of AARL reduction.

- Sol2 at ~€49,000 → AARL ≈ €50,000
- Sol19 at ~€67,000 → AARL ≈ €48,000

Interpretation:

These top-end strategies (e.g., very large parametric policies, full self-insurance) deliver almost no further decrease in expected losses – meaning they are not cost effective anymore. CCLs can use this plateau to argue that once you exceed a certain investment level, funds are better allocated elsewhere (e.g., prevention, recovery planning) rather than marginal risk-financing.

Figure 4.2 Interpretation of the Pareto front for Massa, fluvial flood with (after) EBA, historical climate scenario, 1956-2005.

5. DRF STRATEGIES FOR CCLLS

5.1. General

Following and adopting the DRF chain from understanding risk to its reduction, transfer, and retention are essential to succeeding and forming a cohesive and sustainable DRF strategy. Key considerations and principles in this context include:

- **Layered DRF works.** Core principles are simple: reduce first layer of risk with highest ROI interventions (like EBA), retain and share frequent losses, transfer low-frequency-high-impact losses, accept and plan against losses above a certain resilience target corresponding to a chosen return period.
- **Climate change is increasing the uncertainties** – ergo probability of extreme events. Focus should be shifted from median trends to tail losses to properly manage associated risks. The science behind as well as the datasets are constantly improving and evolving. Therefore, keeping models up to date with the state of the art is imperative for an evidence-based disaster risk financing.

Three climate scenarios¹³ (historical, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5), which are formally adopted by the IPCC, have been used as benchmark for risk assessment in this study. However, for brevity, only the historical and RCP4.5 scenarios are elaborated in this chapter. And we focus on the 2015-2065 timeframe for RCP4.5. Same evaluation logic can be expanded to consider also RCP8.5 and other timeframes by the CCLLs for decision-making purposes.

- While large-scale sovereign pools remain the norm at national level, a handful of pioneering city and regional governments are beginning to experiment with parametric covers—often via public-private partnerships with reinsurers like Swiss Re or specialist InsurTechs. As data infrastructure improves and regulators clarify frameworks (per EIOPA’s recent staff papers), we can expect more European cities to adopt parametric instruments as a routine part of their DRF “layer cake”, bridging the gap between local reserves and slower national disaster funding.
- **Speed vs. basis risk:** Rapid payouts (often within days) support critical services and small businesses, but imperfect correlation between trigger and actual loss (“basis risk”) can leave gaps if, for example, flood depth at a single gauge doesn’t reflect damage across a neighbourhood.
- **Models are useful tools** whose sole purpose is to guide decision-making, not to replace it.

On risk retention (self-financing layer):

- **Municipal contingency reserves:** CCLLs can work towards earmarking dedicated budget lines (“rainy day” funds) sized to absorb high-frequency, low-impact flood events; integrate these into multi-year fiscal planning to avoid reactive cuts to other services. The outlines of the risk layering set out in the present work are meant to help risk managers understand the required size range – that is most cost-effective – of these funds for their planning.

¹³ For descriptions see Chapter 2, Pg. 13.

- **Contingent credit facilities¹⁴**: CCLs should understand the availability of national or regional pre-approved lines. Reserves are often topped-up when credit trigger thresholds are approached, balancing cost of carry against liquidity needs. The existing mechanisms in Europe tend to be either post-disaster solidarity funds (like the EU Solidarity Fund, EUSF¹⁵), programmed investment funds, or developing contingent debt deferral instruments with specific scopes. The primary responsibility and mechanisms for providing immediate post-disaster liquidity to municipalities often remain within national frameworks.

Figure 5.1. Computed fluvial flood loss exceedance curves with EBA are shown for historical and RCP4.5 climate scenarios for the three frontrunner CCLs. 1-in-200 year-loss can be interpreted as the level of loss that is expected, on average, to be exceeded once every 200 years.

On risk acceptance and resilience targets:

- CCLs can set their individual resilience targets to 1-in-200-year loss and plan against them (see Figure 5.1). In other words, losses beyond this threshold are discouraged from being managed actively through ex-ante risk financing.

On risk transfer:

¹⁴ Instrument is not included in our assessment through the DSS Tool.

¹⁵ This is a key instrument for providing financial assistance to EU Member States and accession countries in the aftermath of severe natural disasters. EUSF aid is a form of financial solidarity, supplementing national public expenditure on emergency operations and recovery. However, it is a post-disaster mechanism, requiring an application process after an event, and the funds are managed at the national level, which then channel them to affected regions and municipalities. It is not a pre-approved credit line for sub-national entities

- **Traditional indemnity insurance¹⁶**: Limited by high premiums and slow claims processing for systemic floods — indemnity insurance should be used selectively for critical public assets where parametric basis risk is unacceptable.
- **Parametric products**: Rapid, pre-defined payouts when water-level or rainfall indices breach thresholds. Example: Swiss Re's FLOW water-level insurance, customizable to municipal revenue-loss profiles, delivers liquidity in days. Basis risk must be managed via well designed triggers and spatially distributed sensors that gauge water levels.
- **Subnational risk pools¹⁶**: Pool flood risk across multiple municipalities to diversify local peaks and reduce premiums; emerging literature shows improved cost-effectiveness and reliability for mid-tail events.
- **EU-backed reinsurance partnership**: Following Valencia floods, ECB/EIOPA proposed a bloc-wide public-private reinsurance scheme to cover extreme events beyond national budgets—bridging the protection gap and leveraging sovereign credit. Similar, ex-ante arrangements can be pursued by select CCLs in the future.

¹⁶ Instrument is not included in our assessment through the DSS Tool.

5.2. Guidance for frontrunner CCLs

Illustrative case studies across the consecutive phases of DRF are provided for the three frontrunner CCLs in the following to demonstrate a pathway to improve climate resiliency for a hypothetical next year.

Massa

At a glance

EBA implementation is pivotal; it is estimated to slash average annual loss (AAL) from €750,000 to €25,000 (a 97% reduction), bringing comprehensive risk financing within reach.

With an assumed €200,000 in yearly budget for ex-ante risk financing, the city can make itself resilient against fluvial flooding up to its 1:200 return period resilience target by a mix of retention and transfer. The relatively low levels of frequent return period losses (after highly successful risk reduction through EBA) favour ceding a large chunk of the risk. This is driven by the shape of the EP curve. That is, frequent losses, which are expensive to insure against, are estimated to be very small after risk reduction. Modest reserve top ups (less than 5% of the assumed budget) are expected to be sufficient to cover up frequent residual losses.

Decision-makers are also urged to be cognisant of the uncertainties in tail losses due to climate change: the 200-year fluvial flooding (residual) loss varies from €1 million (historical) to €4.4 million (RCP4.5). This can have significant implications to budget considerations.

Phase	Task	Process	
1	Risk understanding	Exposure	Exposure is made up of a population of 20,474 people, built up area of about 1.13km ² . Transportation includes roads only.
		Hazard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fluvial flooding more prevalent compared to coastal flooding as far as historical baseline is concerned. The increase in the likelihood of extremes caused by increased volatility caused by climate change renders coastal flooding tail hazard to be also high.
		Risk	<p>Massa's climate-risk profile is typical of many small/medium Mediterranean catchments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> frequent flooding (€0.75m per annum historically) that strains the municipal operating budget. With RCP4.5 climate change projections, this figure is extended to €1.5-3.0m range. Climate change imposes massive uncertainties on tail losses. 200-year fluvial flooding loss varies from as low as €1 million (business as usual) to 4.4 million across the <i>historical</i> and <i>RCP4.5</i> climate scenarios (Figure 5.1). <p>With limited fiscal space (we assume a yearly €0.2m for calculations following stakeholder input) and heavy reliance on regional civil-protection transfers, the risk profile characterized by the AARL (i.e., EL) sits comfortably at 3x the yearly budget.</p>

2	Disaster Risk Management	Risk acceptance / Resilience targeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A resilience target in terms of a return period losses needs to be set. This is to ensure that the risk financing and management strategy can manage all disaster losses up to this level. The initial resilience target is recommended at 150- or 200-year loss based on historical or RCP4.5 (2015-2065) climate scenario to be revised in the future if needed. The city can then look to develop a strategy of risk reduction, retention, and transfer that ensures they are able to actively manage all losses up to this resilience target.
		Reduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First layer of risk reduction is pursued in the form of EBA. Massa is estimated to be able to significantly reduce flood risk both in EL and tail (at longer return period) loss terms (both monetary and human) by up to 97%. The residual baseline risk measured by the AARL is estimated to be slashed from €750,000 to €25,000. Cost-benefit analysis for said EBA solution is to be evaluated and later integrated into post-reduction risk financing calculations.
		Retention	Portion of the remaining (residual) post-reduction (i.e., with EBA) risk is to be retained before ceding the remaining risk through market risk transfer.
		Transfer	Remaining risk above retention is transferred up to the resilience target

3	DRF Instrument Design	Risk holder	<p>The city raises capital primarily through local taxes. In Italy there is no line in the national budget that automatically assigns any coastal municipalities a fixed sum each year for disaster-risk management. Instead, all funding for planning, prevention and emergency response is budgeted at the national level—primarily through the Department of Civil Protection (<i>Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri</i>) and a handful of dedicated “<i>funds to be ripartite</i>” managed by the Ministry of Economy and Finance—and then disbursed to Regions, Provinces and Municipalities according to specific criteria and calls for project proposals ex-post. The annual budget should be contrasted to modelled average annual loss (AAL).</p> <p>Each year the Dipartimento della Protezione Civile issues decrees that set out:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Total resources for <i>contributi al volontariato organizzato</i> (€3.5 million in 2024), split 50 % “<i>quota nazionale</i>,” 35 % “<i>quota regionale</i>” and 15 % “<i>quota locale</i>.” Criteria and procedures for granting funds to update or draw up municipal and intermunicipal civil-protection plans. <p>Massa must submit projects in response to these calls; only then can they receive a share of the allocated pot.</p>
		Purpose	Funding is required to support EBA and contributions towards a reserve fund and insurance. Operational funds are for restoring essential services immediately following any disaster, and funding for repair and reconstruction of the physical assets.
		Timing	Funds for risk reduction are required immediately. Funds for restoring essential services should be available as soon as possible following impact, if not before. Funds for reconstruction will be required over the longer term, the speed of financing is not so important, but the funding needs to closely match the loss.
		Risk level	The city aims to make itself resilient for all risk levels, from the frequent attritional losses, up to the 1-in-200-year return period resilience target.

4	Risk finance instruments	<p>Massa can assess the range of DRF options that are available to it.</p> <p>To fund the risk reduction activities,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • it identifies budget allocation, loans, grants, and possibly bonds as viable instruments. <p>Regarding risk retention,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the city identifies budget contingency and reserve funds as possible options. <p>For risk transfer,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The city identifies insurance and national risk pools as appropriate mechanisms. • Bonds are deemed not to be suitable provided Italy does not, to this date, issue or co-sponsor catastrophe bonds at the national level, let alone sub national. <p>With a range of possible options identified, the city now needs to select from these options.</p>
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5	Risk management and finance strategy	<p>Layer 1. Analyses conclusively demonstrated that risk reduction through EBA can dramatically lower the costs of risk retention and transfer instruments in Massa. Finding an appropriate instrument to fund this risk reduction activity should therefore be a priority. We herein assume EBA is implemented before advancing to risk retention and transfer.</p> <p>Layer 2. Bound by its constraints and assumptions¹⁷, risk layering analysis (DSS tool) favours ceding a large chunk of the risk. This is driven by the shape of the loss exceedance curve. That is, frequent losses, which are expensive to insure against, are estimated to be very small after risk reduction. Modest reserve top ups (less than 5% of budget) are expected to be sufficient to cover up frequent losses.</p> <p>Bank loan, bonds, or contingency credit lines are not explored or discussed as part of risk retention given the small scale of the study area and scope.</p> <p>Layer 3. 1-in-200-year tail loss instead ranges €1-4m from baseline to RCP4.5 climate scenario (2015-2065) (see Figure 5.1), which can be financed by parametric insurance, keeping to a yearly budget (see Sol2 for RCP4.5, 2015-2065) of less than €80,000. The total risk of the city owned assets is too small to justify the additional costs required to implement a catastrophe bond or risk pool. The insurance premium quoted to cover all the assets up to the 1 in 200-year resilience target is met by the budget.</p> <p>This can complete the disaster risk financing strategy for the next year, but the city has now identified there are no large protection gaps within its own strategy, and identified a number of additional initiatives which may help to reduce the cost of DRF. Application of an EBA risk-reduction strategy emerged as the top-level priority to achieve financial climate resilience. The city begins to engage with other cities in Liguria (region) to share its DRF experience and explore options for a city-level risk pool which might help it to achieve its resilience targets in future years.</p>
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¹⁷ Refer to discussion in Chapter 4.3 and 0. Key constraints are the reserve fund ceiling of €1 million and a yearly budget of €200,000 dedicated to ex-ante DRF.

Oarsoaldea

At a glance

Extremely high, residual risk characterized by short return period losses (e.g., 1:10-year loss estimated at €16M) after modest risk reduction through EBA impact leave a steep protection gap with average annual residual loss estimated at €3.5M. In other words, the city would struggle to reach even a 1-in-5-year resilience target, facing a protection gap of approximately €10 million (in annual net residual loss) beyond the protection secured by the assumed annual budget of €200,000 through retention and transfer.

The city needs to almost exclusively rely on state and international aid to bridge its protection gap, which is much less efficient, costlier, and slower. Risk layering analysis suggests – regardless of budget – prioritizing the first layer of further risk reduction activities on the back of Cost-Benefit Analysis. Residual risks can then be financed with lower costs through a mix of retention and transfer.

The city should also explore ways to benefit from regional/sovereign risk pools in case risk reduction efforts do not gain traction.

	Phase	Task	Process
1	Risk understanding	Exposure	Oarsoaldea, located in Spain, has a population of 70,808, built-up areas covering approximately 1.87 km ² , an extensive road network of 484.5 km, and 33.5 km of railway infrastructure. The region faces significant exposure to fluvial flooding, particularly pronounced within the densely populated urban sectors.
		Hazard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fluvial flooding is the focus of this assessment.
		Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The baseline annual average loss (AAL) due to fluvial flooding is approximately €3.5 million, which stresses the municipal budget. City exhibits a very flat EP curve (see Figure 5.1). That is, frequent (1-in-10) loss is estimated at €16m, while tail loss (1-in-200-year loss) at €31m. Climate projections under RCP4.5 (2045-2095) suggest tail risks associated with rare, high-impact flooding events (e.g., 1-in-200-year events) are subject to modest – if not negligible – amplification.
2	Disaster Risk Management	Risk acceptance / Resilience targeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A resilience target in terms of a return period losses needs to be set. This is to ensure that the risk financing and management strategy can manage all disaster losses up to this level. The initial resilience target is recommended at 150- or 200-year loss based on historical or RCP4.5 (2015-2065) climate scenario to be revised in the future if needed. The city can then look to develop a strategy of risk reduction, retention, and transfer that ensures they are able to actively manage all losses up to this resilience target.
		Reduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First layer of risk reduction is assumed to have been already implemented in the form of EBA in this work. Our assessment suggests that the explored EBA in Oarsoaldea yields a modest reduction in baseline risk. Cost-benefit analysis for said EBA solution should be evaluated and integrated into post-reduction risk financing calculations.

		Retention	Oarsoaldea's risk layering strategy incorporates municipal reserve funds dedicated to absorbing higher-frequency flood losses, allowing budget stability and operational continuity post-event. Reserve targets and replenishment rates are set within fiscally prudent bounds, aligning with stakeholder preferences.
		Transfer	Risk exceeding the municipal retention threshold – which is capped at €1m – is transferred through insurance mechanisms up to the resilience target. Parametric insurance, characterized by predefined and rapid payouts, is recommended to complement traditional indemnity insurance due to its efficacy in covering residual risk from severe events.

3	DRF Instrument Design	Risk holder	Funding primarily originates from local taxation, complemented by national and regional funds allocated through disaster-response frameworks. Oarsoaldea aims to leverage these funding avenues efficiently to maintain fiscal resilience.
		Purpose	Funding is required to support EBA and contributions towards a reserve fund and insurance. Operational funds are for restoring essential services immediately following any disaster, and funding for repair and reconstruction of the physical assets.
		Timing	Funds for risk reduction are required immediately. Funds for restoring essential services should be available as soon as possible following impact, if not before. Funds for reconstruction will be required over the longer term, the speed of financing is not so important, but the funding needs to closely match the loss.
		Risk level	The city can aim to make itself resilient for all risk levels, from the frequent attritional losses, up to the 1-in-200-year return period resilience target. However, under RCP4.5 (2015-2065) climate scenario, 1-in-200-year loss corresponds to €38.5 million (as opposed to 'business as usual' counterpart of €31m; see Figure 5.1), which is in excess of the maximum retention level capped at €1 million in reserves.

4	Risk finance instruments	<p>The city can assess the range of DRF options that are available to it. To fund the risk reduction activities, it identifies the following instruments from the DRF taxonomy: budget allocation, loans, and possibly government bonds.</p> <p>Regarding risk retention,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the city identifies budget contingency and reserve funds as possible options. <p>For risk transfer,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The city identifies insurance and national risk pools as appropriate mechanisms. Bonds are deemed not to be suitable provided Italy does not, to this date, issue or co-sponsor catastrophe bonds at the national level, let alone sub national. <p>With a range of possible options identified, the city now needs to select from these options.</p>
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5	Risk management and finance strategy	Risk layering	<p>Layer 1. Our analyses showed that the explored EBA leads to only a tiny reduction of risk. Therefore, the city should strongly consider exploring alternate risk reduction solutions. Selecting an instrument to fund the risk reduction activity should be among core activities. We herein assume EBA is implemented before advancing to risk retention and transfer.</p> <p>Layer 2. Bound by its constraints and assumptions¹⁸, risk layering analysis using the developed DSS tool suggests retaining most of the risk through reserves with yearly budget maxed out at the assumed maximum of €200,000 (see Sol2 in the delivered Pareto Front for RCP4.5 climate scenario). More importantly, however, frequent, 1-in-10-year (fluvial) flooding loss is estimated at €16m, which far exceeds the maximum assumed reserve capacity of €1 million.</p> <p>The total risk of the exposure in the city might justify the additional costs required to implement a regional risk pool. However, risk-reduction through alternate measures is best explored first.</p> <p>Bank loan, bonds, or contingency credit lines are not explored or discussed as part of risk retention given the small scale of the study area and scope.</p> <p>Layer 3. Frequent losses are extremely costly to insure and best retained to remain cost-effective and operationally efficient. Therefore, the optimal solutions err on the side of only a small insurance coverage. The average annual residual risk remains extremely high around €3.5 million, reflecting a budget shortfall in financing existing flood risk. Depending on the strategy choice (e.g., Sol11), tail loss estimated at €38.5m (RCP4.5, 2015-2065) suggest that the city would be unable reach even a resilience target of 1-in-5 years with a protection gap and budget shortfall of 16.0m – 1.0m – 4.8m ≈ €10m. This translates into a roughly €3.5m AARL that will need to be financed through state or EU-level intervention and aid (ex-post).</p> <p>This can complete the disaster risk financing strategy for the next year. The city has now identified where there are protection gaps lie – largely within the first risk-reduction layer – and identified a number of additional initiatives which may help to reduce the cost of DRF. The city begins to engage with other cities in the region to share its DRF experience and explore options for a city-level risk pool which might help it to achieve its resilience targets in future years.</p>
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¹⁸ Refer to discussion in Chapter 4.3 and 0. Key constraints are the reserve fund ceiling of €1 million and a yearly budget of €200,000 dedicated to ex-ante DRF

Vilanova

At a glance

Despite significant risk reduction from EBA (cutting expected losses from €4M to €1.8M – over 50% reduction), residual frequent losses (1-in-10-year loss estimated at €8.7M) still overwhelm retention and transfer instruments that can be arranged with a yearly (assumed) budget of €200,000. Losses only up to barely 1:5 years can be financed without increasing this budget. The average annual net residual losses would be financed by ex-post state or international aid at a much higher cost and lesser effectiveness.

In addition to needing a budget increase, Vilanova is incentivized to first explore further cost-effective risk reduction measures at both city, and critical infrastructure levels. Then, city- or region-level risk pools or other meso-layer risk retention mechanisms such as contingent credit lines to complement its risk layering strategy.

Vilanova is also estimated to be subject to large uncertainties associated with climate change. RCP4.5 climate scenario (2015-2065) calculations indicate a potential 33% increase in computed tail loss with respect to historical assumptions (business-as-usual scenario) about which the city needs to be cognisant.

Phase	Task	Process	
1	Risk understanding	Exposure	Vilanova i la Geltrú, located in Spain, has a population of 58,501, built-up areas covering approximately 1.67 km ² , a substantial road network of 460.7 km, and a railway infrastructure of 22.2 km.
		Hazard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fluvial flooding is the focus and the by far largest contributor to floods in Vilanova.
		Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The baseline annual average loss (AAL) due to fluvial flooding is approximately €4 million, which is a large burden on the municipal budget, without national aid and funds and likely exceeds Vilanova's municipal budget The city exhibits a fairly standard EP curve with a large difference between frequent and rare losses. Based on 'business as usual' estimates without climate change, 1-in-10 and 1-in-200-year losses are estimated at €5m and €18m, respectively (see Figure 5.1). Climate projections under RCP4.5 (2015-2065) lead to nearly 33% increase in computed tail loss.
2	Disaster Risk Management	Risk acceptance / Resilience targeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A resilience target in terms of a return period losses needs to be set. This is to ensure that the risk financing and management strategy can manage all disaster losses up to this level. The initial resilience target is recommended at 200-year loss based on historical or RCP4.5 (2015-2065) climate scenario to be revised in the future if needed. The city can then look to develop a strategy of risk reduction, retention, and transfer that ensures they are able to actively manage all losses up to this resilience target.
		Reduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First layer of risk reduction is recommended in the form of EBA – same as all CCLs. Suggested EBA is estimated to notably slash risk (e.g., €1.8m in EL from €4.0m; north of 50% reduction in tail loss) across the risk metrics and climate scenarios and is recommended to be prioritized. Cost-benefit analysis for said EBA solution should be evaluated and integrated into post-reduction risk financing calculations.

		Retention	Risk layering strategy incorporates municipal reserve funds dedicated to absorbing higher-frequency flood losses, allowing budget stability and operational continuity post-event. Reserve targets and replenishment rates are set within fiscally prudent bounds, aligning with stakeholder preferences.
		Transfer	Risk exceeding the municipal retention threshold – which is capped at €1m – is transferred through insurance mechanisms up to the resilience target. Parametric insurance, characterized by predefined and rapid payouts, is recommended to complement traditional indemnity insurance due to its efficacy in covering residual risk from severe events.

3	DRF Instrument Design	Risk holder	Funding primarily originates from local taxation, complemented by national and regional funds allocated through disaster-response frameworks. Vilanova aims to leverage these funding avenues efficiently to maintain fiscal resilience.
		Purpose	Funding is required to support EBA and contributions towards a reserve fund and insurance. Operational funds are for restoring essential services immediately following any disaster, and funding for repair and reconstruction of the physical assets.
		Timing	Funds for risk reduction are required immediately. Funds for restoring essential services should be available as soon as possible following impact, if not before. Funds for reconstruction will be required over the longer term, the speed of financing is not so important, but the funding needs to closely match the loss.
		Risk level	The city can aim to make itself resilient for all risk levels, from the frequent attritional losses, up to the 1 in 150- or 200-year return period resilience target.

4	Risk finance instruments	<p>The city can assess the range of DRF options that are available to it. To fund the risk reduction activities, it identifies the following instruments from the DRF taxonomy: budget allocation, loans, and possibly bonds.</p> <p>Regarding risk retention,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the city identifies a reserve fund as possible option. <p>For risk transfer,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The city identifies insurance and national risk pools as appropriate mechanisms. Bonds are deemed not to be suitable provided Italy does not, to this date, issue or co-sponsor catastrophe bonds at the national level, let alone sub national. <p>With a range of possible options identified, the city now needs to select from these options.</p>
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5	Risk management and finance strategy	Risk layering	<p>Layer 1. Analyses showed that the explored EBA leads to a significant reduction of risk and therefore can be pursued by the city. Selecting an instrument to fund the risk reduction activity should be among key activities. We herein assume EBA is implemented before advancing to risk retention and transfer.</p> <p>Layer 2. Bound by its constraints and assumptions¹⁹, risk layering analysis using the developed DSS tool suggests retaining most of the risk through reserves with yearly budget maxed out at the assumed maximum of €200,000 (see Sol1 in the delivered Pareto Front for RCP4.5 climate scenario). Frequent, 1-in-10-year (fluvial) flooding loss is estimated at €8.7m, which is in excess of the maximum reserve fund size of €1 million.</p> <p>Contingency credit lines are not explored or discussed as part of risk retention given the small scale of the study area and scope.</p> <p>Layer 3. Frequent losses are extremely costly to insure and best retained to remain cost-effective and operationally efficient. Therefore, the optimal solutions such as Sol1 on the Pareto Front for the RCP4.5 (2015-2065) err on the side of minimal insurance coverage. The average annual residual risk remains high around €1.10-1.65 million (historical to RCP4.5), which needs to be met by ex-ante state or international aid at a much higher cost for lesser effectiveness.</p> <p>This can complete the disaster risk financing strategy for the next year. The city has now identified where there are protection gaps lie. Namely, a large protection gap across all DRF layers including the ability to absorb frequent losses without having to tap into national risk pools. The city begins to engage with other cities in the region to share its DRF experience and explore options for a city-level risk pool which might help it to achieve its resilience targets in future years.</p>
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¹⁹ Refer to discussion in Chapter 4.3 and 0. Key constraints are the reserve fund ceiling of €1 million and a yearly budget of €200,000 dedicated to ex-ante DRF

5.3. Guidance for follower CCLs

The financial resilience strategies for Coastal City Living Labs (CCLs) outlined in this report highlight several critical themes and lessons learned from extensive evaluations across multiple cities. Understanding these recurring themes is essential to optimizing disaster risk financing (DRF) strategies tailored to specific local contexts.

Risk Reduction as a Primary Strategy

One of the principal findings from the analysis underscores the significant impact that risk reduction can have on lowering DRF costs. The extent to which risk can be mitigated—particularly through Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) explored in this study—varies significantly among different CCLs, reinforcing the importance of rigorous risk assessment. Consistent with risk-layering principles, proactive risk reduction should always form the foundational layer of any DRF strategy. Addressing frequent, smaller-scale risks through targeted risk reduction measures significantly diminishes the residual risk that must subsequently be managed through financial instruments, thus lowering the overall cost of risk financing.

For example, in Massa, Italy, Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) solutions dramatically reduced projected flood risks by up to 97%, lowering annual average losses from approximately €750,000 to just €25,000. Although the follow-up Cost/Benefit Analysis will reveal how cost-effective this solution truly is, it has been repeatedly demonstrated around the globe that ex-ante risk reduction interventions must precede financial instruments to effectively manage residual risks.

Significance of the Loss Exceedance Probability (EP) Curve

The [EP curve](#) is a crucial factor in determining the optimal mix between risk retention and risk transfer. Each CCL presents a unique risk profile with distinct EP curves, emphasizing the necessity of thorough, data-driven risk quantification. Effective financial strategies depend on understanding these curves to appropriately balance retained risk and transferred risk, particularly via parametric insurance products which are most cost-effective when tailored to local risk dynamics. Resilience targets are commonly set at the 1-in-200-year loss, using the EP curve. This targeted resilience approach in turn guides focused risk transfer strategies; particularly market transfer of risk – through a combination of parametric insurance and, if feasible, cat bonds – solutions designed to match the city's risk profile precisely.

Context-Specific Resilience Targets

Setting appropriate resilience targets is inherently context-specific and heavily influenced by stakeholders' risk appetite and the criticality of infrastructure within each community. Stakeholder engagement is thus vital to defining resilience targets that reflect local priorities and financial capacities. Clear, realistic resilience targets guide municipalities in structuring their financial instruments, determining the levels of retained and transferred risks, and setting acceptable thresholds for risk acceptance. Resilience targets are also great, evidence-based performance indicators for tracking a city's progress towards achieving climate resilience.

Leveraging Contingent Credit

Contingent credit lines are effective second-layer risk retention instruments. Compared to maintaining large reserve funds, contingent credits offer a more efficient mechanism to finance moderate-frequency events, providing access to liquidity post-event without the substantial opportunity costs associated with holding large cash reserves indefinitely.

Most CCLLs are likely to have no access or experience with such instruments. However, as we see it, this is a missed opportunity for the CCLLs to reduce their disaster losses at lower costs. Although not explicitly evaluated in this study, empirical evidence and good practices around the world converge on its key role as a meso-layer in layered risk financing. As such, we encourage municipalities to push for regional, or EU-level contingent credit agreements to significantly enhance their climate resilience in Europe.

Flexibility and Diversification of Financial Instruments

The assessments highlight the benefits of flexibility and diversification in financial instruments. Municipalities are advised to diversify their risk portfolios by using a combination of instruments—including insurance, bonds, contingency credits, and reserves—to effectively manage different layers and types of risk. Flexibility in strategy design allows cities to adjust financial arrangements rapidly as their risk profiles and market conditions evolve.

Utilizing EU-Level Risk Pools and Catastrophe Bonds

Exploration and implementation of EU-level catastrophe bonds or regional risk pools offer promising mechanisms to bridge financing gaps, particularly in regions susceptible to significant climate risks. Collective risk pooling can leverage economies of scale, diversify risks across larger geographic areas, and substantially lower premium costs for individual municipalities.

While concrete examples of dedicated regional or city-level catastrophe (CAT) bonds for weather-related perils in Europe remain scarce, there is a growing and urgent call from financial institutions and risk management experts for their development and adoption. The increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, coupled with a significant insurance protection gap, are driving the need for innovative financial solutions to bolster the resilience of European municipalities and regions²⁰.

Experts and institutions like the European Central Bank (ECB) and the European Systemic Risk Board (ESRB) strongly advocate for greater use of CAT bonds at all levels, including regional and city, to address the widening gap between economic losses from weather events and insured losses. The outcomes of this study support these notions by providing evidence to their potential. However, the focus will likely remain on creating enabling frameworks, fostering expertise, and encouraging pioneering municipalities – like the CCLLs in this study – and regions to explore these financial tools to better protect their communities and economies from the escalating threat of weather-related disasters.

Dynamic Adaptation to Macroeconomic Conditions

Financial resilience strategies cannot remain static. Annual reassessments are essential as macroeconomic conditions—such as fluctuations in insurance market cycles and changes in opportunity costs—impact the optimal composition of DRF instruments. Flexible, periodically reviewed strategies allow CCLLs to adjust their financial management practices dynamically, ensuring sustained resilience and cost-effectiveness over time.

²⁰ Currently, the European landscape for CAT bonds is more developed at the sovereign and supra-national levels, with entities like the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) playing a role in promoting climate resilience financing. For instance, the EBRD has plans to extend Climate Resilient Debt Clauses (CRDCs) to municipal clients, which could offer financial relief after extreme weather events, though these are not strictly CAT bonds in the traditional sense.

Communication and Coordination with National and EU Institutions

The effectiveness of local DRF strategies is significantly enhanced by strong communication and coordination with national and EU entities. Transparent communication about financing gaps helps shift perceptions from reactive, ex-post funding mechanisms toward proactive, ex-ante financial planning. This shift is essential to reduce delays in disaster response and improve overall efficiency.

Comprehensive Approach for CCLs

The insights gleaned from the frontrunner CCLs collectively underscore the importance of comprehensive, evidence-based strategies. Effective DRF strategies integrate robust risk reduction, layered financial instruments, clearly defined resilience targets, and flexible adjustment mechanisms sensitive to evolving macroeconomic conditions.

In conclusion, the optimal disaster risk financing approach combines robust risk assessment, strategic risk reduction, judicious risk retention—including contingent credit options—and targeted risk transfer through carefully designed parametric products. Continuous stakeholder engagement, regular strategic reassessments, and strengthened EU collaboration emerge as key practices to ensure resilience and fiscal sustainability across Europe's coastal communities.

6. APPENDIX A: DECISION SUPPORT TOOL

To derive a set of Pareto optimal alternatives, we conducted a simulation-based Multi-Objective (MO) optimization using a 20,000-year Monte Carlo simulation. This method employs random sampling to model and analyse the impact of uncertainty across different scenarios, allowing for a thorough evaluation of each strategy's performance. In this context, the Monte Carlo simulation helps identify the best strategies by simulating thousands of potential outcomes and balancing multiple objectives. The process was organized as follows.

6.1. Dataset preparation

We generated a Monte Carlo dataset, comprising 20,000 years of stochastically independent and identically distributed realizations. The first step involved fitting the simulated loss data points, which delineate the risk curve from Task 6.3 to an appropriate distribution. Several potential distributions were tested (see Figure 1), and the best-performing one, the Piecewise Cubic Hermite Interpolating Polynomial (PCHIP), was selected. Using this distribution, we generated 20,000 years of synthetic data to ensure a comprehensive and robust dataset for the Monte Carlo simulation.

This dataset serves as the historical as-if cash flow data from the "business as usual" scenario (scenario before the implementation of any financial strategy) and it provides the baseline financial losses that the strategies are intended to manage. This dataset serves as input to the optimization and was organized into 1,000 realizations, each spanning 20 years, enabling us to assess the performance of strategies over short to medium-term horizons.

6.2. Optimization objectives

The optimization aimed to minimize two primary objectives:

1. **Total Financial Strategy Cost:** This includes the insurance loading (the actual cost of insurance policies) and the opportunity cost of the strategy. Opportunity cost refers to the value of the best alternative use of resources, such as investments, that are forgone by allocating liquidity to the reserve fund or insurance premia.
2. **Average Annual Residual Loss (AARL):** This measures the losses that remain uncovered after the implementation of the strategy, which has significant socio-economic and political implications. Minimizing AARL is crucial to ensuring the strategy effectively mitigates residual risks.

To formalize these objectives, we define:

$$StrategyCost = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Total\ Cost^{(i)}, \quad AARL = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Residual\ Loss^{(i)}$$

Where:

- i indices each of the $N = 1,000$ independent Monte Carlo scenarios,
- Total Cost(i) is the average yearly cost of the strategy in scenario i ,
- Residual Loss(i) is the average yearly residual loss in scenario i .

Each scenario consists of 20 years of financial data. For each scenario i , the *Total Cost* and *Residual Loss* are calculated as follows:

$$\text{Total Cost}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\text{OC}_{\text{premium}}^{(t)} + \text{OC}_{\text{reserve}}^{(t)} + \text{Loading} \right)$$

$$\text{Residual Loss}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(L_{\text{residual}}^{(t)} \right)$$

Where:

- $T = 20$ is the number of years in the scenario.
- $\text{OC}_{\text{premium}}^{(t)}$ is the opportunity cost of the insurance premium in year t . This is the cost of not investing the premium money, assuming a long-term interest rate of 5%. It is calculated as:

$$\text{OC}_{\text{premium}}^{(t)} = 0.05 \times \text{Insurance Premium}$$

- $\text{OC}_{\text{reserve}}^{(t)}$ is the opportunity cost of the reserve fund in year t . It reflects the cost of not investing the reserve money, again assuming a 5% return rate:

$$\text{OC}_{\text{reserve}}^{(t)} = 0.05 \times \text{Reserve Fund}$$

- The insurance Loading is typically calculated as proportional to the standard deviation of the covered losses. We used a loading factor of 15%:

$$\text{Loading} = 0.15 \times \text{Std}(\text{Covered Losses})$$

- $L_{\text{residual}}^{(t)}$ represents the residual loss in year t , i.e., the portion of the loss that is not covered by the insurance or reserve fund.

Where:

- $\text{Loss}_{\text{residual}}^{(t)}$ is the financial loss in year t
- Coverage_t is the combined coverage from the reserve fund and insurance in year t .

$$L_{\text{residual}}^{(t)} = \max(0, \text{Loss}_t - \text{Coverage}_t)$$

6.3. Optimization variables

The key decision variables optimized in this process included:

- x_1 : Maximum capacity of the reserve fund: [0, 1,000,000]
- x_2 : Yearly reserve fund intake: [0, 1,000,000]
- x_3 : Proportion of losses ceded to insurance: [0, 1]
- x_4 : Insurance attachment point, above which coverage starts: [0, ExhaustionPoint]

where $\text{ExhaustionPoint} = \min(10,000,000\text{€}, \text{loss at 200-year return period})$

These variables define the layered financial risk management strategy, determining the balance between immediate liquidity and long-term financial stability.

Figure 6.1. Risk curve fitting

6.4. Constraints

The optimization also includes two key constraints to ensure financial feasibility:

Budget Constraint: The combined cost of the annual reserve intake and the insurance premium must not exceed a predefined maximum annual budget. This is formulated as:

$$x_2 + \text{insurance premium}(x_3, x_4) \leq B_{\max}$$

Where $B_{\max} = 200,000\text{€}$.

Reserve Fund Constraint: The yearly intake into the reserve fund cannot exceed the maximum reserve capacity:

$$x_2 \leq x_1$$

These constraints ensure that each financial strategy remains realistic and implementable under existing fiscal limitations

6.5. Optimization method

The simulation-based multi-objective optimization problem was solved using an evolutionary algorithm (NSGA-II). Evolutionary algorithms are highly effective for MO problems, drawing inspiration from natural evolutionary processes like selection, crossover, and mutation. These algorithms start with a diverse set of potential solutions, each representing different combinations of decision variables such as budget allocation between reserve funds and insurance premiums.

To assess each solution, the algorithm evaluates its performance 1,000 times across a 20-year horizon, focusing on minimizing the total financial strategy cost and the Average Annual Residual Loss (AARL) in each scenario. The best-performing solutions are selected to form the next generation, mimicking natural selection. Through crossover, parts of selected solutions are combined to create new ones, mixing and matching traits to potentially produce better outcomes. Mutation introduces small random changes to maintain diversity and explore new areas in the solution space.

This process of selection, crossover, and mutation is repeated over many generations, with the population of solutions gradually improving. The algorithm converges towards the Pareto front, representing a set of optimal solutions where no single objective can be improved without worsening the other. For our problem, this means finding the best trade-offs between minimizing financial costs and residual losses.

6.6. Pareto Optimal Solutions

Solutions on the Pareto front represent optimal trade-offs between minimizing the total strategy costs and AARL. Ideally, the most favourable solutions are positioned in the lower-left corner of the Pareto front, indicating strategies with both low insurance costs and minimal residual losses. Solutions above the Pareto front are considered suboptimal within our defined criteria, while those below are deemed unfeasible or beyond computational limits or the problem definition. 20 solutions were homogeneously sampled from the optimal front for further analysis and comparison (see Figure 2).

Figure 6.2 Example of a Pareto front

7. APPENDIX B: INFOGRAPHICS

A set of infographics summarizing the key aspects of the developed financial strategies for the frontrunner CCLs, as well as a set of general guidelines that can underpin the development of such strategies for municipalities exposed to climate-related risks, are provided in this Appendix.

Investing in Climate Adaptation

Enhancing Massa's Climate Resilience

Disaster Risk Financing (DRF) Guidelines Aims: This strategy provides financial guidelines to help manage the increasing risks of climate-related disasters.

Flood Risk in Massa

- **Hazards:** Historically dominated by fluvial floods, but coastal flooding is an increasing concern.
- **Loss Estimates:** Average annual flood losses range from €0.75 - €3.0M before any risk management action is implemented.
- **Fiscal Exposure:** With no pre-allocated national funds, Massa competes for regional civil protection funding, heightening vulnerability.

Key Recommendations for Managing Risk

1. Risk Reduction - Prioritise EBAs to reduce overall risk & financing costs. *Implement Ecosystem-Based Adaptations (EBA) that reduce hazard exposure. In Massa, EBAs could cut average annual losses by 97%, reducing costs to €25,000.*

2. Risk Retention - Reserve funds can cover frequent, low-severity losses. *Thanks to the hugely successful risk-reduction layer provided by EBAs, risk retention would require modest savings, only a small fraction of the estimated budget.*

3. Risk Transfer - Use parametric insurance for high-impact events. *For rare, high-impact floods, parametric (index-based) insurance is recommended. Residual losses for rare (1-in-200 year) events can be covered for under €80K/year.*

Investing in Climate Adaptation

Enhancing Oarsoaldea's Climate Resilience

Disaster Risk Financing (DRF) Guidelines Aims: This strategy provides financial guidelines to help manage the increasing risks of climate-related disasters.

Flood Risk in Oarsoaldea

- **Hazards:** Exposed to fluvial flooding, particularly within its dense urban areas.
- **Loss Estimates:** Baseline average annual losses are around €3.5 million. Frequent (1-in-10-year) events could result in €16 million in losses, while a rare (1-in-200-year) event could cause €31–38.5M in damages.
- **Fiscal Exposure:** A dedicated budget to address high frequency (1-in-10-year) losses is lacking, creating a critical protection gap.

Key Recommendations for Managing Risk

1) Risk Reduction - Prioritise Expanded Measures Beyond EBAs. Risk reduction must be prioritised. The implemented Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBAs) provide only modest reductions. Additional risk reduction options to be explored to meaningfully reduce the cost of forecasted risks.

2) Risk Retention - Use Reserve Funds Where Feasible. Without further risk retention capacity, the city may require ~€16 million/year in reserve fund capacity to absorb frequent event costs. Aim to cover these with adequate reserve funds, explore collaborative risk pools within the region, and event-contingent credit lines.

3) Risk Transfer - Use a Layered Insurance Approach. On top of traditional insurance, use parametric (index-based) insurance to cover excess risk - around €20 million in coverage is needed to reach its resilience goals.

Investing in Climate Adaptation

Enhancing Vilanova's Climate Resilience

Disaster Risk Financing (DRF) Guidelines Aims: This strategy provides financial guidelines to help manage the increasing risks of climate-related disasters. D

Flood Risk in Vilanova i la Geltrú

- **Hazards:** Dominated by fluvial flooding, the city's primary climate hazard.
- **Loss Estimates:** Baseline average annual flood losses are approximately €4-5M. This is anticipated to strain the municipal budget.
- **Climate Projections:** Climate change may raise rare and severe losses to €24M, a 33% increase.

Key Recommendations for Managing Risk

1) Risk Reduction - Prioritise EBAs to lower risks and financing costs. Vilanova i la Geltrú has implemented Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBAs), which has effectively reduced expected annual losses from €4M to €1.5M. Despite this, residual risk remains high, warranting further structural or EBA risk reduction.

2) Risk Retention - Use reserves for frequent, low-severity losses. The city needs around €5M in retention capacity to cope with frequent (1-in-10-year) post-EBA losses. The city could explore regional collaborative risk pools or event-contingent credit lines for frequent events that exceed municipal reserves.

3) Risk Transfer - Use parametric insurance to cover rare, high-severity losses. The region should focus on building the financial ability to handle smaller, more frequent events. Then, utilise parametric (index-based) insurance for the more severe and rare events.

Disaster Risk Financing Guidelines

Making Every Euro Count

Disaster Risk Financing (DRF) Guidelines Aims: This strategy provides financial guidelines to help manage the increasing risks of climate-related disasters.

1) Prioritise Risk Reduction

Risk reduction, especially through Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA), is the most cost-effective strategy. In Massa (IT), EBAs cut average annual losses by over 95%. Global evidence affirms that reducing risk up front lowers overall financing needs and should always be the first DRF layer.

3) Set Specific Resilience Targets

Resilience targets should reflect local priorities, risk appetite, and critical infrastructure. Engaging stakeholders ensures realistic goals, helping cities allocate between retained, transferred, or accepted risks effectively.

5) Diversify and Stay Flexible

A mix of instruments, reserves, insurance, contingent credit, and possibly bonds, enhances flexibility. As risks and markets evolve, annual reviews of DRF strategies ensure continued relevance and cost-effectiveness.

7) Risk Pools and Catastrophe Bonds

Though still rare, EU-level catastrophe bonds and risk pools hold promise. CCLs can lead innovation by exploring regional pooling and capital market solutions.

2) Use Exceedance Probability Curves

Loss exceedance probability (EP) curves are central to risk-layering. It identifies return-period losses (e.g., 1-in-200-year) to inform resilience targets and determine which risks to retain or transfer. Parametric (index-based) insurance can be tailored to match the local EP curve and offer fast payouts after major events.

4) Explore Contingent Credit

Resilience targets should reflect local priorities, risk appetite, and critical infrastructure. Engaging stakeholders ensures realistic goals, helping cities allocate between retained, transferred, or accepted risks effectively.

6) Engage EU & National Institutions

CCLs should take the lead in initiating dialogue with their national, regional, and EU-level counterparts to emphasize the importance of evidence-based DRF, which is significantly more cost-effective and operationally efficient.

8) Reassess Regularly

DRF strategies must adapt to macroeconomic shifts, including insurance market cycles and funding conditions. Regular reassessment helps cities remain resilient and fiscally sustainable.

